

The Waste Tip

Understanding fly-tipping:

the complexities of definition, measurement,
inequalities and urban infrastructure

Executive summary

Fly-tipping is a core issue for many local authorities and wider government. In 2022/23 local authorities in England dealt with 1.08million fly-tipping offences (Defra, 2023). This not only uses up valuable local authority resources, but it also has a detrimental effect on local communities and ecosystems.

Despite the problems that fly-tipping creates, there is a dearth of research and data on the practice. Yearly Defra statistics are produced but these are based only on what is reported and as we demonstrate there are issues with how fly-tipping is measured and accounted for. Studies to date similarly focus solely on quantitative data rather than using qualitative methods to provide more in depth attempts to understand why fly-tipping occurs. This lack of insight is problematic meaning that experiences of fly-tipping are not accounted for in strategies put forward to deal with it. Whilst many think of fly-tipping as being the domain of unscrupulous commercial outfits leaving industrial waste in rural places and by the sides of roads, available data suggests that 60% of fly-tipping involves household waste (Defra, 2023). Yet again there is a lack of engagement with those experiencing household fly-tipping to be able to fully address the problem.

This report draws on a qualitative pilot study working with waste professionals whose remit it is to deal with fly-tipping. Whilst only small scale in terms of size, our in depth interviews and work shadowing with these professionals illuminate three core findings:

- i. Difficulties defining fly-tipping stem from issues around what constitutes fly-tipping and where it is found.
- ii. Issues with measurement and responsibility further compound (i) and highlight gaps in current waste infrastructure.
- iii. Inequalities and urban infrastructure exacerbate fly-tipping and must be considered in future strategies.

Our key recommendations are twofold: Firstly, that infrastructure must be adequate and consistent to measure and deal with fly-tipping and that this requires funding. Secondly, and more broadly, that prevention must be a priority. However, for this to be achieved requires moving beyond current behavioural change approaches in waste policy to take better account of the context of people's everyday circumstances and how those circumstances can lead to fly-tipping.

To cite this report:

Holmes, H. and Perczel, J. (2024) 'The Waste Tip. Understanding fly-tipping: the complexities of definition, measurement, inequalities and urban infrastructure', Sustainable Futures, The University of Manchester. Available at: 10.5281/zenodo.11057447.

Introduction

The Waste Tip was a pilot project funded by the University of Manchester, to explore the phenomenon of fly-tipping using a qualitative social science approach. Fly-tipping in the UK is a criminal offence that denotes the practice of residents and businesses depositing their household waste or bulky wastes on roadsides, fields, and alleyways instead of the designated bins or collection centres. To date, research on fly-tipping has been predominantly from a quantitative perspective – seeking to measure fly-tipping incidents, and, in some cases, public perception, through surveys and data capture. Furthermore, much of this work is now outdated with the large majority of studies taking place over a decade ago.

The Waste Tip sought to address this research gap by examining the challenges of fly-tipping, particularly household fly-tipping, through an in depth qualitative design including interviews, work shadowing and participant observation. Centred on Greater Manchester, this 12-month pilot project worked with local authority waste professionals to grasp the complexities of fly-tipping and specifically to attempt to understand the ‘who, what, where’ and ‘when’ of fly-tipping incidents.

In what follows we discuss our key findings. We argue that there are three interconnected aspects which must be considered to tackle household fly-tipping practices. These include: (i) the complexity of defining fly-tipping incidents, (ii) issues of measurement and responsibility; and (iii) the role of socio-economic factors and the influence of the built environment. We conclude with a suggestion that moving beyond a focus on behaviour change and taking account of the complexities of social practice offers a way forward to tackle household fly-tipping.

Fly-tipping in the UK

Fly-tipping in the UK is a persistent problem for local authorities. In 2022/23 there were 1.08 million fly-tipping events in the UK (Defra, 2023). Whilst this marked a 1% decrease from 2021/22 there has been a gradual increase in fly-tipping over the past decade with the peak year being 2020/21, in the midst of the pandemic, with a marked rise to 1.1m incidents. It is also worth noting, and as we discuss in what follows, such figures only take into account reported incidents, and therefore figures are potentially higher. Alongside fly-tipping, littering is also a key waste occurrence with 2.25 million pieces of litter estimated to be dropped in the UK everyday (Keep Britain Tidy, 2023). 60% of fly-tipping involves household waste (Defra, 2023) which dispels the perceived narrative that the majority of fly-tipping is large-scale and commercial. As we discuss, a core issue is side waste. This is waste left at the side of bins by households.

There is dearth of information on fly-tipping. Data sources from Defra and third sector NGOs (Keep Britain Tidy, 2023; Dsposal, 2018) provide core insights into the scale of fly-tipping but often do not address the more qualitative, on the ground or unreported aspects. Likewise, the majority of academic studies on fly-tipping are 10-20 years old, focused on commercial fly-tipping and are also quantitative in their approach – with little assessing qualitative impacts. This is likely because gathering qualitative data is time consuming and resource intensive, aspects which are exacerbated when the subject matter is highly sensitive and ethically problematic to research.

Quantitative academic work on commercial fly-tipping has focused on the criminal aspects and its economic motivations (Watson, 2005) or more broadly environmental impacts (Webb et al, 2006: 7). The only academic study to date which has addressed household fly-tipping has also been quantitative, involving surveying 900 households in Hampshire, alongside local authority and third sector organisations. The study found that bulky items were most likely to be fly-tipped, that highways and rural locations were the most popular locations and that fly-tipping was more likely to be considered an issue in areas of high deprivation, population density and with a large proportion of rented accommodation. We pick up on some of these findings in what follows. However, our qualitative analysis extends further enabling us to analyse the social factors, impacts and, importantly, lived experiences, of fly-tipping. The recency of our study enables us to assess fly-tipping as part of the contemporary waste landscape, a landscape which has changed over the last 10-20 years due to a variety of factors affecting local authorities (e.g. reductions in waste budgets, changes to waste targets), waste management organisations (e.g. an increased focus on recycling, reuse and energy from waste) and households (e.g. the increasing complexity of waste regimes).

The Research

The research which underpins this report took place between September 2022 and August 2023 and was supported by a University of Manchester UMRI grant. The project's aim was to conduct a pilot project to gain qualitative insight into fly-tipping as a phenomenon with a focus on the experiences of waste professionals who were dealing with such waste as part of their roles. Our research was conducted in the North-West of England and involved 12 in-depth interviews with 14 waste professionals, alongside site visits and work-shadowing. Participants were recruited using a snowball sampling strategy and drawing on the authors' existing networks.

The waste professionals interviewed hold a variety of roles including waste officers, street cleansing operatives, enforcement professionals and local councillors. Due to the short duration of the project the decision was taken to not engage with local residents, specifically because of the ethical requirements that this would require. We recognise this as a limitation of our data and emphasize the need for further study which does engage with local residents in an in depth and qualitative way. As noted, our data focuses almost entirely on household forms of fly-tipping, as this was perceived as the main issue for the waste professionals we spoke to. Most interviews lasted between 1-2 hours each being audio-recorded and professionally transcribed before being analysed and thematically coded.

Our Findings

Finding 1: 'Is it fly-tipping?': Why the 'what' and the 'where' matter

Key points

- Whilst the legal definition of fly-tipping is clear how that plays out in practice between households and local authorities is much more subjective.
- Side waste is a continued area of contestation between local authorities and households.
- Gardens, yards and unregistered land are spaces of contestation with regards fly-tipping and who is responsible. Whilst charity shop collections further illuminate how 'the street' is considered local authority space.
- Fly-tipping 'hotspots' illuminate persistent locally known areas of dumping. In some respect these represent informal, yet illegal, waste management infrastructure, as patterns of dumping by fly-tippers and clearing by the local authority persist.

Issues of definition

Legally fly-tipping is defined as the 'illegal disposal of household, industrial, commercial or other 'controlled' waste (Smith, 2023). Whilst this definition is clear and concise, our research found that this regularly breaks down in practice due to ambiguities and differences in classification. Classifying waste is an important part of a local authority's reporting duties, enabling local, regional and national level statistics on the types of waste produced and how this waste is processed/recycled. We found that issues of definition are ultimately based on 'the what' and 'the where' of fly-tipping. In other words, what the abandoned items are and where they are left influences how they are categorised and, as discussed in the next finding, measured and dealt with. However, as we demonstrate this is fraught with subjectivity.

Side waste

One particular aspect which challenges the definition of fly-tipping is side waste. This is rubbish which is placed either at the side of bins or within communal waste areas. The key point being that this is waste which is left in very close proximity to formalized sites of waste collection. Often this waste might be an extra black bin bag of household waste or a small household item.

Most of our participants acknowledged that this is small-scale, fly-tipping behaviour and is not for financial gain. Yet it is still classed as fly-tipping. Under the duty of care as defined in law any producer of waste has the responsibility to deal with their waste according to section 46 of the Environmental Protection Act. Waste outside of the

"When you say fly-tipping, I think it kind of covers a number of different types of activity. Is it someone just throwing an extra bin bag in the back alley... because they've not got enough room in the bin and they're not recycling? Is it because they've got a wardrobe and they don't have a car and they think the best way to do it because they don't want to pay for a bulky collection is to put it in the back alleyway?"

"A lot of fly-tipping is how you class fly-tipping, most councils now have a fairly strict policy. [...] Some people will then put out an extra black bag or if you have a lot of terraced properties they will have a communal collection point and then put all the bins out and leave a few black bags. Most councils are pragmatic and say to the waste collectors, 'Just take them,' because otherwise you will be reporting it, but essentially it is fly-tipping."

bin, regardless of size or contents, is classed as ‘fly-tipped’ and can be investigated to establish ownership and invoke a fixed penalty notice.

Yet as a recent Keep Britain Tidy report (2023) concluded many households do not view waste left out on the street as fly-tipping. The street is seen as the public domain of the local authority and waste left by the side of bins an extension of those bins. In this regard, households think they are doing the right thing by placing extra rubbish at the side of bins.

Shrinking general waste bin sizes in the UK are part of wider local authority behavioural change strategies to encourage recycling. Side waste is an example of how such policies are not working. As the first author discusses elsewhere (Holmes et al., 2023), smaller general waste bins can lead to households feeling forced to find alternative options for excess waste – such as ‘hiding’ waste in recycling bins, using the bins of neighbours without their knowledge, or contributing to side waste.

Contestations over public versus private space

Just as side waste illuminates how there are contestations over categorising fly-tipping based on ‘where’ it is left and ‘what’ it is constituted of so these public/private contestations play out in other spaces:

Gardens and yards

Accumulations in ‘private’ outdoor spaces attached to homes are deemed problematic incidents by waste professionals, often leading to reports by members of the public of fly-tipping. However, categorising such incidents as fly-tipping and dealing with them as such is difficult. The boundaries between public and private spaces are assumed to be ‘mutually exclusive and exhaustive’ defined by ‘spatial markers’, such as fences, gardens and yards (Blomley, 2004: 281, 283). Yet whilst spaces such as gardens and yards may be legally determined as ‘private’, in practice such spaces are more fluid.

Charity collections

Items left out on the street by households for charities to collect can potentially be deemed as fly-tipped waste by local authorities and reported as such. Although households do not perceive the item as waste and may think they are doing the right thing by moving the item along to someone else (Holmes, 2023), the local authority may not realise this and once again the space of the street becomes a contested area of waste management and ownership.

Unregistered land

Fly-tipping on land where there is an owner but no registration of them further adds to the public/private distinction. Local authorities have a responsibility to clear waste from council properties or what are called ‘adopted highways’ – privately owned roads which are dedicated to public use. However, if fly-tipping occurs on sites which are privately owned but there is no record of the owner then the local authority must try to find them to deal with the waste. This can cause tensions with local residents who may view the land as public and therefore the responsibility of the local authority.

‘Hot spots’: informal, illegal, efficient(?) waste management

The issue of contested space is further extended by the notion of fly-tipping ‘hotspots’. As other research (Webb et al., 2006) has suggested, certain spaces become known as areas of fly-tipping and this informal, local understanding of spaces of dumping further exacerbates the issue. Sometimes referred to as the ‘broken window theory’ (Webb et al., 2006) this is an idea that spaces already in disrepair encourage other forms of anti-social behaviour. Yet our participants clearly stated that part of the issue with fly-tipping hotspots is that they are dealt with and cleared up too quickly. This suggests that areas become known as ‘acceptable’ places to dump things and in a strange way an informal waste management system emerges between residents and the local authority.

This is also interesting given the number of historical dumping sites in and around Greater Manchester. Historical UK landfill maps (The Environment Agency, 2020) indicate that there are approximately 20,000 historic landfill sites around the UK, pre-dating contemporary environmental regulation with some dating back to the Victorian era (Cooper, 2008; Jackson, 2014). Greater Manchester has numerous sites dotted in and around the city and its suburban areas. Whilst there is no academic research on how these spaces map on to current fly-tipping hotspots – anecdotal evidence suggests that such habitual spaces of dumping can persist. A potential opportunity for future research would be to overlay a map of current hotspots over that of the historical sites to determine any synergies.

“The problem is now that we’ve created this expectation that we will do this all of the time.”

“The difficulty as a council is that you want people to stop dumping rubbish, but we will clear away the rubbish if people dump it.”

Finding 2: ‘Who’s responsible for dealing with it?’: Issues of measurement and responsibility

Key points

- Measurement of fly-tipping is not consistent across different areas due to resource and target pressures, infrastructural issues and subjectivities around classification.
- Prosecuting those responsible is fraught with difficulties due to issues with finding sufficient evidence, potential intimidation of witnesses, and slow judicial processes.

Measurement

Our research found that the measurement of fly-tipping is often not consistent due to subjectivities regarding classification (as discussed above), alongside other pressures such as targets and a lack of resource. Side waste is particularly problematic with regards to whether it is measured as fly-tipping or not, with participants noting how some local authorities may class it as such, whilst others may not. Likewise, often this decision comes down to the team on the ground dealing with waste and whether they report waste as fly-tipping.

Issues with systems

As many of our participants discussed part of the problem with measuring fly-tipping is due to infrastructural issues and systems which are not sophisticated enough to categorise different ‘types’ of waste occurrences. Meaning that sometimes fly-tipping waste may end up being rolled into other types of waste categories.

Issues with resource

Whilst systems may be too clunky to deal with different waste occurrences, other pressures occur due to lack of resource. The drastic cutting of local authority budgets is well documented and waste departments have ultimately felt the pinch from this. As one participant noted, dealing with fly-tipping is relentless with teams working 10 hour days 363 days of the year. The overall UK national increase in fly-tipping incidents (noting that figures declined slightly in 2022/23) will undoubtedly place further pressure on over-stretched local authority resources.

The recycling trap

Measurement can also be affected by pressures to reach specific government set targets. Our participants discussed how pressures to meet recycling targets meant that local authorities would often feel forced to classify side waste as fly-tipping. To collect side waste as part of kerbside collections increases overall general waste tonnage, and therefore impacts on general waste to recycling ratios. Therefore,

there is little incentive for local authorities to collect side waste if it ultimately affects their overall recycling performance.

Responsibility

Difficulties with prosecution

Our participants spoke at length about the difficulties in holding those responsible for fly-tipping accountable. Focusing primarily on commercial and larger scale forms of fly-tipping (not side waste) participants raised issues regarding finding sufficient evidence, potential intimidation of witnesses and accidental fly-tipping where unscrupulous commercial contractors dump waste from work they have done for households or other businesses and those households/businesses then get blamed (see also Dsposal, 2018 report on waste crime). As one participant noted, it ‘can take 18 months before it goes through to our legal team to process it to court for prosecution’ and often cases are ‘inadmissible in court’. Thus, finding those responsible and holding them accountable is fraught with difficulty.

“A lot of fly-tipping will go unreported, some people will report a carrier bag full of waste as fly-tipping, strictly speaking it probably is, whereas councils will log it as that but some councils might not choose to.”

“So if we’ve got a number of jobs to be doing, we’ll go to that job and then we’ll go to that job and then we’ll go that job and then we’ll clean up and clear up. Now fly-tipping might be job number 2 or job number 5 or job number 7 but we haven’t got very sophisticated systems.....to, well, split up what the definition of fly-tipping is out of our actual operation.....I think the data you’re probably dealing with has so many variables and considerations it’s difficult to actually say this is fly-tipping and this is how much there is of it.”

“We’re challenged to hit 55% and that number will go up. If you want to give yourself half a chance of doing that, then you can’t collect fly-tipping. If you collect everything presented around the bins, that will increase the tonnages of your general waste stream which will mean that percentage wise, you are recycling less.”

Finding 3: ‘Where is it occurring and why?’: issues of inequality and urban infrastructure

Key points

- Household fly-tipping is not just economically motivated but is interwoven with a range of inequalities.
- Areas of social deprivation, transient populations and temporary, short-term housing are deemed to be factors which increase fly-tipping practices.
- Ensuring waste policy takes account of complex lives and multiple inequalities will be crucial to tackling fly-tipping.
- Urban infrastructure plays a key part in exacerbating fly-tipping practices – high density housing, criss-crossed with alleyways and narrow paths make waste management difficult.
- Community collaboration can play a part in tackling fly-tipping, particularly through the management of neighbourhood areas prone to fly-tipping. However, this must be supported with resource.

Inequalities

In trying to understand the ‘why’ of fly-tipping many of our participants initially stated that they believe fly-tipping (commercial and household) is economically motivated. This was thought to be people not interested in ‘doing the right thing’ when there is a cost associated to it. However, when we began to unpack this question, it came to light that participants were aware of varying and interwoven inequalities which influence household waste disposal practices and can lead to fly-tipping. We discuss these in turn but must stress that they are very much interconnected and overlapping:

Social deprivation

The majority of our participants indicated that fly-tipping was highest in the most socially deprived areas. Not having the resources to pay for bulky collections or access to transport to be able to move items to the nearest materials recovery facility are aspects of inequality which often get overlooked when considering why fly-tipping occurs. With the continued cost of living crisis finding an available £30-£50 to pay for bulky waste collection or transport to remove items are not options for those having to make daily decisions about whether to ‘eat’ or ‘heat’.

Housing tenure

Our research found that housing tenure can also play a part in fly-tipping practices but that this is related to other issues and inequalities. Rented accommodation, illegally sublet by unscrupulous landlords often to transient populations (see below) and potentially missing the right bins or relevant waste information can exacerbate fly-tipping practices.

Transient populations is another factor participants deemed to increase fly-tipping practices. As we discuss in what follows, this can be exacerbated by potential communication and language barriers, alongside, as we have discussed previously, issues of subletting and lack of appropriate infrastructure or information. As other studies have demonstrated, temporary accommodation can have a significant impact on a person or household’s ability to engage in waste management regimes (Timlett and Williams, 2009). Short-term residencies with high turnovers of tenants do not encourage engagement with local authority waste management rules. As participants noted, when engagement does occur and does work ‘then they (residents) are moving on six months later. So you start the whole process again.’

Communication and digital inequalities

As we have alluded to above, issues with and barriers to accessing waste information is another reason our waste professional participants give for residents engaging in fly-tipping. This could be issues related to the landlord not passing on such information, language barriers (Oluwadipe et al., 2022) making it difficult for residents to understand already complex waste regimes (Holmes et al., 2023), or difficulties accessing online information about waste infrastructure. Digital inequality is a prevalent issue in the UK with both data poverty and lack of digital skills being key issues. Estimates suggest that 1.7 million households cannot access the internet and 2.4m people lack the skills to do a basic online task (UK Parliament, 2023). Without access to waste information fly-tipping is likely to occur.

Complex lives

At the heart of this section is the need to recognise the complexity of people’s lives. It is likely that it is not just one form of inequality or issue which pushes a household to engage in fly-tipping, but rather a range of intersecting inequalities. This tallies with other research which emphasizes that if households are facing multiple social and economic pressures waste management is not a high priority and fly-tipping or side waste may be more likely to occur (Martin et al., 2006; Oluwadipe et al., 2022). Recognising this complexity and tackling related inequalities must be part of wider waste strategies to deal with issues such as fly-tipping.

“You can see when you look at the different areas that there is a big disparity between the richer end. A lot of this is linked to cash, and the poorer side ad deprivation that comes with that. That flows into all different facets in people’s lives to do with health and outcomes and stuff. Waste is a symptom of that.”

“A lot of properties, terraced houses, are rented, and it’s not always a legitimate landlord. There’s an awful lot that have probably been sublet. When they sublet the property might not have correct bins. [...] We have a lot of areas with transient populations, so 3–6-month rentals...”

If people come from a war-torn country or come as a refugee, an asylum seeker, rubbish is the least of their worries, they could be facing all kinds of traumas, they may never have been told how to use the bins, the information may all be in English, they may not have access to any kind of digital equipment.

“We seem to get it a lot when it’s terraces because they’ve got no front gardens, very tiny rear yards, nowhere to store anything...”

“Because we’ve got a lot of terraced properties and we’ve got a lot of quite tight areas, community areas[...] if they’ve got more rubbish than they can fit in their bins, obviously this kind of comes out as either side waste or fly-tipping.”

Urban infrastructure

The built environment is another factor in understanding the ‘why’ of fly-tipping and cannot be easily separated from issues of inequality. As our participants discussed, the urban landscape has significant effects on fly-tipping practices.

Housing type

Houses without front or back yards, such as terraces and flats, were seen to be more at risk of fly-tipping because of a lack of storage capacity for waste. Having nowhere to store bulky items for removal or excess waste that will not fit in bins means that often such waste ends up in communal areas and on the street.

High density housing

Linked to housing type, density of housing was also determined as a factor in increasing fly-tipping. As other research concurs, tightly packed locations with multiple households often conjoined by narrow alleyways and communal waste areas make waste management difficult (Dsposal, 2018). This includes problems with contamination in shared communal waste spaces due to incorrect use of bins, waste being left as side waste or in alleyways. This can be exacerbated by density of the built environment making it difficult for both local authority waste vehicles to access waste and for residents having to move bins around to get it collected at the kerbside.

Community managed alleyways

Many of our participants discussed the vital role that local residents often play in preventing fly-tipping. As other research has found, there are areas where residential groups work collectively to clear up alleyways and other communal spaces to prevent fly-tipping and create shared community spaces (MacGregor, 2021). As one participant noted, we have residents ‘out there every day looking at what is going on, challenging new tenants, knocking on the doors, telling them what they should do’. Thus, collective investment by local residents, engaging with other neighbours, offering advice and creating communal spaces can be an important part of tackling fly-tipping practices. However, as we discuss in the summary, this must be supported with resource.

Summary

This report illuminates the complexity of household fly-tipped waste. Drawing on the experiences of waste professionals its findings focus on three broad issues which make dealing with fly-tipping difficult: (i), the complexity of defining fly-tipping incidents, (ii) issues of measurement and responsibility; and (iii), the role of socio-economic factors and the influence of the built environment. These three broad findings encompass more specific and complex issues linked to who, what, where and why of fly-tipping.

Importantly, findings (i) and (ii) highlight issues with current waste infrastructure and its abilities to deal with fly-tipping. Subjectivities, differing practices and lack of resources within local authorities mean that reporting, measuring and dealing with fly-tipping is at times inconsistent and siloed. This can not only result in a lack of accurate data at a local authority level but also on a much larger national level, as local authority level data is aggregated. Our first recommendation is that waste infrastructure requires funding to be able to adequately define and consistently measure fly-tipping incidents.

Our second recommendation is focused on preventing fly-tipping. Whilst the above advocates for funding to ensure better data capture of fly-tipping events, preventing fly-tipping in the first instance also requires more adequate data, and particularly in depth qualitative data. Finding (iii), in particular, attempts to unpack some of the complexity of why fly-tipping occurs. We argue that fly-tipping prevention strategies need to move beyond current behavioural change approaches to take better account of the context of people’s everyday circumstances and how those circumstances can lead to fly-tipping. As our research has shown, behavioural change approaches of ‘one size fits all’ do not account for the diversity and complexity of people’s lives – be that the restrictive urban design of the neighbourhood they live in, their housing tenure and type, or the multiple inequalities they may face on a daily basis.

The positive results of community managed neighbourhood spaces offer a potential opportunity for fly-tipping prevention (MacGregor, 2019), but we strongly caution that these voluntary activities must not be seen as removing the onus from local and national policy stakeholders in the way other forms of community ‘assets’ have been. Providing local communities with the tools, continued support and resources to establish such spaces is paramount. Holistic waste policy which takes into account household diversity and facilitates and supports local residents in adhering to waste regimes is required.

Acknowledgments

This report is based on the findings of the project: 'The Waste Tip: Exploring fly-tipping and opportunities for better waste management' funded by a University of Manchester UMRI Grant.

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To cite this report

Holmes, H. and Perczel, J. (2024) 'The Waste Tip. Understanding fly-tipping: the complexities of definition, measurement, inequalities and urban infrastructure', *Sustainable Futures*, The University of Manchester. Available at: 10.5281/zenodo.11057447.

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